

Synthesis of Ethyl 3-Phthalimidoacetoacetate

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Ethyl 3-phthalimidoacetoacetate (IV) was first prepared by Gabriel (*Ber.*, 1909, 42, 1244; 1913, 46, 1706). To study the synthetic applicability of this compound, it was prepared by Gabriel's method in poor yield, attended with large amounts of unidentified byproducts among which two were isolated—one melting at 90–95° and the other at 116°. The identification of these compounds is still being carried out. The difficulty in the separation of these compounds led us to modify Gabriel's method. Thus ethyl 3-phthalimidoacetoacetate was prepared in 63% yield when, instead of sodium, ethoxymagnesium derivative of diethyl malonate (I) was used. Further, it had been found that ethyl 3-phthalimidoacetoacetate could be obtained in similar yields even without isolating the intermediate compound, diethyl phthalimidoacetomalonate (III).

Diethyl Phthalimidoacetomalonate.—In a one-liter, three-necked flask, containing 7 c.c. of dry ethanol and 1 c. c. of dry CCl_4 , was placed 6.25 g. (0.258 g. atom) of clean Mg. A mixture of diethyl malonate (40g., 0.25M) and dry ethanol (20 c.c.) was then added at such a rate that a vigorous reaction was maintained. When the evolution of hydrogen had subsided, dry ether (70 c.c.) was added and the mixture gently refluxed till all the Mg had dissolved. On removal of the solvent under diminished pressure the residue was dissolved in dry benzene (75 c.c.) and the latter removed as above. The residual syrup was dissolved in dry ether (75 c.c.) and phthalimidoacetyl chloride (56 g., 0.25 M), dissolved in dry ether (500 c.c.), was added to it with brisk stirring to maintain the vigour of the reaction. Finally the reaction mixture was refluxed for 1½ hours and then cooled. To the mixture 10% H_2SO_4 (100 c.c.) was added to decompose the MgCl -complex. The organic layer was separated and washed successively with H_2SO_4 (dil., 20 c.c.), water (2×20 c.c.), 5% NaHCO_3 (10 c.c.), and water (2×10 c.c.). Ether was removed when a slightly brown-coloured semisolid residue (86 g.) was obtained. The latter was rubbed with ethanol (10 c.c.) and chilled in ice. The precipitated *diethyl phthalimidoacetomalonate* was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 68° (lit. m.p. 68°), yield 55g. (Found: C, 58.61; H, 4.90; N, 4.30. Calc. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_7\text{N}$: C, 58.8; H, 4.9; N, 4.03%).

Ethyl 3-Phthalimidoacetoacetate.—The pure diethyl phthalimidoacetomalonate (55 g. or 86 g. of the crude semisolid residue obtained above) was steam distilled and then the

whole was extracted with benzene. The organic layer was filtered through cotton wool and the solvent removed. The residue was twice recrystallised from ethanol, when 43 g. of white needle-shaped crystals of the pure product, m.p. 110° (lit. m.p. 110°), was obtained. The yield amounted to 63% (Gabriel had not mentioned the yield), calculated on the basis of the acid chloride used. (Found: C, 60.98; H, 5.30; N, 4.98. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{13}O_5N$: C, 61.10; H, 4.73; N, 5.08%). This compound is soluble in hot ethanol, glacial acetic acid, ether, and benzene; its ethonolic solution developed a red colour with aq. $FeCl_3$, deepened on standing. *Semicarbazone* was obtained from ethanol as a white crystalline solid, m.p. 164° (Found: C, 54.01; H, 4.80; N, 16.61. $C_{15}H_{16}O_5N$ requires C, 54.22; H, 4.82; N, 16.87%).

Pyralazone was obtained from ethanol as a white crystalline solid, m.p. 177° (Found: C, 67.39; H, 4.46; N, 13.06. $C_{18}H_{15}O_3N_3$ requires C, 67.29; H, 4.73; N, 13.08%).

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